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ESIWACE3 Newsletter

Issue #1 / June 2023

News

Call for Proposal 2023-2024

On 28 April 2023, the first ESIWACE3 Call for Proposals (CfP) was published to apply for support from the Consortium research engineers. The aim of the call is to support the exascale preparations for the European Earth System Models (ESM) community. The goal is to improve model efficiency and readying the software to enable model execution on existing and near-future hardware architectures. The call will run from 1 May 2023 at 14:00 h CEST until 1 November 2023 at 14:00 h CET. The CfP is open to all groups developing and maintaining ESM codes (not only the ESIWACE3 partners).

Read more [here](#).

The poster features the ESIWACE logo at the top, followed by the title 'Call For Proposals 2023-2024'. It includes a globe, a line graph, a server rack, a QR code, and a speech bubble with the text '#CfPESIWACE3 #CallForProposalsESIWACE3'. A large arrow points to the QR code with the text 'Apply here!'. Below the QR code is a list of details:

- **What?** Weather and Climate model developers
- **What?** Support, guidance, and advice by the HPC experts of ESIWACE3 in optimizing and porting model source codes to modern HPC systems
- **Where?** Remotely
- **When?** Next deadline **28 June 2023 13:00 CET**

At the bottom, there are logos for partners: DLR, SMHI, ECMWF, ESMValTool, EuroHPC, STFC, LUT, EVIDEN, JÜLICH, and the European Union.

ESiWACE3 at the ISC23

ESiWACE3 was present at the [ISC High Performance 2023](#) (ISC23) event, thanks to the booth that the EuroHPC JU had at the event as an exhibitor. ISC is the most significant European HPC Conference and Exhibition, which occurred this year on 21 - 25 May in Hamburg (Germany). Peter Dueben (ECMWF) gave a short presentation about ESiWACE3 on Monday, 22 May. Furthermore, brand-new ESiWACE3 audiovisual material presenting the project, produced by ESiWACE3 Consortium partner [Latest Thinking](#), was also displayed.

Read more [here](#).

“The ESiWACE3 week” media campaign

A social media campaign to present the new phase of ESiWACE was conducted from 22 to 25 May 2023. Called “The ESiWACE3 week”, the campaign consisted of a series of posts which included videos that presented, briefly and concisely, the main objectives of the project, summarised the KOM celebrated in February, and explained the tasks to be performed within each project's work package by their leaders. The videos were posted on the project's [YouTube](#) channel, and the promotional campaign was carried out through the project's [Twitter](#) and [LinkedIn](#) social networks. With almost 4,000 impressions on LinkedIn, about 3,600 visualisations on Twitter and more than 350 on YouTube, we consider the campaign a success!

See the campaign [here](#).

“Running weather and climate models on LUMI” The 1st ESIWACE3 Hackathon

Registration has opened for the 1st ESIWACE3 Hackathon, entitled “[Running weather and climate models on LUMI](#)”. The event is aimed at helping climate scientists port and optimise their codes to new architectures, such as [LUMI](#). It will take place on 18-20 October 2023 at the [CSC](#) premises in Espoo (Finland) and will be an on-site event—with no remote participation possibility. It is open to anyone who is a member of an organisation eligible to receive an allocation for LUMI compute resources, and groups with Early Career Scientists (ECS), women, and researchers from [ITC countries](#) are especially encouraged to apply. There is no attendance fee.

Read more [here](#).

The banner features logos for eFlows4HPC, esiwace, and Climateurope2 at the top. The main text reads "1ST ESIWACE3 HACKATHON" and "RUNNING WEATHER & CLIMATE MODELS ON LUMI" with dates "18-20 October 2023 - CSC, Espoo (Finland)". Below this, it says "FREE EVENTS" and "EFLOWS4HPC + ESIWACE3 + CLIMATEUROPE2 WORKSHOP" with the subtitle "HPC WORKFLOWS FOR CLIMATE MODELS" and dates "17 October 2023 - CSC, Espoo (Finland)". At the bottom, there are logos for CSC, BSC (Barcelona Supercomputing Center), a QR code, a green arrow pointing left with the text "Info here!", EuroHPC, and the European Union flag.

“HPC workshop for climate modelling”

The first ESIWACE3 Hackathon will be organised in tangent with the workshop “[HPC workflows for climate modelling](#)” by the [eFlows4HPC](#) European HPC project in collaboration with [ESiWACE3](#) and [Climateurope2](#). It will be held at the Dogmi meeting room of CSC on 17 October 2023. It is a one-day free event and aims to find synergies between the three communities. Even if the hackathon and the workshop are organised hand by hand, attendance at both events is independent; hence, there is the option to apply to attend either or both events.

Read more [here](#).

The banner features the eFlows4HPC logo and website "www.eflows4HPC.eu" at the top. The main text reads "ESiWACE3 hackathon" and "Workshop: HPC workflows for climate models" with dates "Espoo - 17 October 2023". Below this, it says "As part of the ESIWACE3 hackathon thanks to the collaboration with:" followed by logos for esiwace and Climateurope2. The background is a pattern of white and yellow geometric shapes.

“#MeetESiWACE3Partners” campaign

To maximise the visibility of the project, on 19 June, a social media campaign started to present the ESiWACE3 Consortium partners and their involvement in the project. It is called “#MeetESiWACE3Partners” and will run until 7 July. The campaign consists of a post per day for three weeks, presenting each day one of the partners of the Consortium and its role within the project. The campaign is accumulating, so far, more than 2,000 visualisations on Twitter and more than 450 impressions on LinkedIn.

Retrieve the campaign [here](#).

Events

Internal events

ESiWACE3 Kick-Off Meeting

On 1 and 2 February 2023, the Kick-Off Meeting of ESiWACE3 was held on the Barcelona Supercomputing Center (BSC) premises in Barcelona. It was opened by Francisco Doblas-Reyes, head of the Department of Earth Sciences at BSC, and Mario Acosta, co-leader of the Computational Earth Sciences group at the Earth Science Department, both project co-coordinators, setting the stage and context. Their welcome and introduction were followed by invited presentations on the [ENES-RI](#) by Fanny Adloff (DKRZ), the thematically neighbouring CoE [ChEESE](#) (Centre of Excellence for Exascale in Solid Earth) by Josep de la Puente (BSC), the obligations of Horizon Europe-funded projects by Linda Gesenhues (EuroHPC JU), as well as introductory presentations on all seven ESiWACE3 work packages and an invited presentation on [Destination Earth](#) delivered remotely by Nils Wedi (ECMWF). The meeting was complemented by diverse breakout groups, including debriefing and a dedicated session on management and coordination.

External events

External events in which ESIWACE3 has participated since the last issue of the ESIWACE Newsletter:

- [EuroHPCSummit](#), Göteborg (Sweden), 20-23 March 2023. [Presentation](#) & [poster](#).
- CASTIEL2: CoEs and NCCs online meeting, virtual, 18-19 April 2023. [Presentation](#).
- [EGU 2023](#), Vienna (Austria) & virtual, 23-28 April 2023. [Slide show](#).
- [ISC23](#), Hamburg (Germany), 21-25 May 2023. [Presentation](#).
- [PASC23](#), Davos (Switzerland), 26-28 June 2023. [Presentation](#).

Updates

Hereby there is the list of the ESIWACE3 deliverables and milestones published within the period M1-M6 (January 2023 and June 2023):

Deliverables

- **Deliverable 6.1: Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation Plan (CDEP)**

D6.1 include the initial plan with the communication, dissemination, community engagement, and exploitation activities to be conducted during the project. It is a live document that will be updated as the project and its necessities evolve.

Read D6.1 [here](#).

- **Deliverable 7.1: Project management guidelines**

D7.1 describes the management and administrative procedures of the project in order to facilitate efficient project execution and ensure high-quality project results. It provides the ESIWACE3 Consortium with a concise reference to the project management structure, tasks, and responsibilities at all levels of project execution.

Read D7.1 [here](#).

- **Deliverable D7.2: Data Management Plan (DMP)**

D7.2 describes how data will be managed within the project and follow-up process. This document will be updated in the following deliverables, including potential modifications to improve data management.

Read D7.2 [here](#).

- **Deliverable D7.5: Collaboration Plan with the definition of common objectives and activities, including milestones**

D7.5 is a collaboration plan with the other Centers of Excellence (CoEs) and National Competence Centers (NCCs), as well as the Coordination and Support Action (CSA) CASTIEL. Update the available applications and different versions deployed via the common platform as an annexe of the management report.

Read D7.5 [here](#).

Milestones

- **Milestone 4.1: First call for projects in Service 1**
- **Milestone 5.1: Event calendar on training is online**
- **Milestone 6.1: Network mapping and engagement strategy ready for CDEP**

Open positions

Research Software Engineer for HPC Applications at DKRZ

[DKRZ](#) is searching for a Research Software Engineer (any gender) for HPC Applications. As part of an international team of HPC experts from a supercomputer vendor and research engineers specialising in software for science, the selected candidate will work to improve the efficiency of selected weather and climate codes and prepare the software to run on existing and near-future hardware architectures. The work will be structured in collaborative projects of six to twelve months, in which the ESIWACE3 team of experts will provide engineering effort, advice, and knowledge transfer to the code owners.

More information about the position [here](#).

News from the neighbours

"Correctness and Reproducibility for Climate and Weather Software" workshop

On 9-10 September 2023, the [National Center for Atmospheric Research](#) (NCAR; Boulder, USA) will host the "Correctness and Reproducibility for Climate and Weather Software" workshop. It aims to provide a

venue to discuss challenges, opportunities, and recent advances in ensuring software correctness and reproducibility for climate and weather modellers, HPC community members, and industry partners. The workshop will be held in person, with a virtual option, at the [Mesa Laboratory](#) of the NCAR.

More info [here](#).

“Machine learning for numerical weather predictions and climate services”

The workshop “Machine learning for numerical weather predictions and climate services” for [ECMWF](#)'s Member States will be held on 27-28 September 2023 in Reading (UK). This two-day workshop for the national meteorological services of ECMWF's Member States aims to evaluate the collective progress and continue to plan for the future machine learning roadmap that ECMWF started in 2021. The workshop is restricted to two in-person Member State representatives per country and ECMWF staff.

More info [here](#).

20th ECMWF workshop on high-performance computing in meteorology

[ECMWF](#) will hold the 20th Workshop on HPC in Meteorology in the historic city of Bologna on 9-13 October 2023. The theme of this year's edition of the workshop is "Diversifying HPC", aiming to explore the challenges and opportunities faced by the weather & climate community, identify the diversity in the technology being deployed in delivering solutions (heterogeneous/modular computing), and increase assortment regarding the future of supercomputing both with hybrid on-premise/cloud integration and alignment with AI/ML community developments.

More info [here](#).

MNHACK23: 5th MareNostrum Hackathon

The fifth edition of the Marenostrum Hackathon, held at the [Barcelona Supercomputing Center](#) (BSC) premises from 16 to 20 October 2023, will be co-located with the 2nd [“EuroHPC Workshop/hackathon on Dynamic Resources in HPC”](#). The MNHACK23 aims to help HPC developers and users with their codes and executions. Participants will be mentored from many disciplines, including computer and domain science. They will have access to the resources of the general-purpose cluster of Marenostrum IV and the GPU-enabled CTE-Power cluster. If Marenostrum V is already in production, participants can also run their codes on the new supercomputer.

More info [here](#).

2nd “EuroHPC Workshop/hackathon on Dynamic Resources in HPC”

Co-located with the [5th Marenostrum Hackathon \(MNHack23\)](#), the 2nd “EuroHPC Workshop/hackathon on Dynamic Resources in HPC” will be an interactive event that will help to align the research and production direction of multiple EuroHPC projects, including DEEP-SEA, EuPILOT, ADMIRE, REGALE, and TIME-X. The workshop aims to implement malleable applications, gain a common understanding of the use cases and their requirements, establish commonly shared terminology, and identify elements that can be moved to a standardisation process, like via the MPI API.

More info [here](#).

LUMI course

The Comprehensive General LUMI course is a four-day hybrid course that comprehensively introduces the LUMI architecture and programming environment. It will include lessons on compiling and using software, programming models (HIP and OpenMP offload), porting, executing jobs, and optimising applications to run on AMD MI250X. After completing the course, you can work efficiently on both the CPU (LUMI-C) and the GPU partition (LUMI-G). It will take place from 3 to 6 October 2023 and can be attended in person in Warsaw (Poland) and online.

More info [here](#).

MAELSTROM Dissemination workshop + Boot Camp

On 7 November 2023, a dissemination workshop about the [MAELSTROM](#) project will be organised at the ECMWF premises in Reading (UK). There will be an overview of the project, followed by invited talks from experts from the three domains of machine learning, high-performance computing, and Earth sciences to summarise and disseminate the latest research and developments towards highly efficient, scalable machine learning tools that improve weather and climate predictions. The workshop will be hybrid, with the possibility to join virtually from everywhere in the world. The MAELSTROM Dissemination Workshop is organised back-to-back with the [MAELSTROM Boot Camp](#). This three-day Boot Camp aims to train the participants to use machine learning (ML) in weather and climate applications on High-Performance Computing systems (HPC). The participants will get an introduction to meteorology, ML, and HPC scientific domains. The target participants are Master's and PhD students and early career scientists. It will be held on 8-10 November 2023 at ECMWF premises in Reading (UK).

More info about the workshop [here](#) and about the Boot Camp [here](#).

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